

The Indian Epistemic Equilibrium A Catalytic Paradigm for Global Science-Religion Dialogue

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Abstract: After taking a panoramic view of the India scientific tradition particularly from the perspective of astronomy, mathematics and medicine the author discusses some of the central epistemological tenets of the India scientific tradition, which is accountable for its ontological proximity with philosophy and religion culminating in a scientifically warranted spiritual holism. He concludes the article with some observations on what the global science-religion momentum can benefit from the science-religion equilibrium of India. The author is of the view that the emerging interdisciplinary attempt needs to be enhanced by transferring its scope and spheres to more substantial and metaphysical domains of truth. The India paradigm where the science-religion dialogue itself is part of a wider spectrum of the manifestation of truth could be helpful in this regard.

Keywords: Ayurveda, India Science, Global Scene, Science-religion Dialogue.

Introduction

Dilip M. Salwi's *Nonsense in Indian Science*, published by Konark Publishers Pvt. Ltd. in 1998 does a paradoxical practice by printing an apology in the place normally devoted to a preface. The apology goes on to say: "there is no such thing as 'Indian science' or 'Australian science' or for that matter 'Western science.' Science is science - the country where it is practiced does not matter. In this book,

'Indian science' refers to the typical cultural practices followed by Indian scientists."² If we accept the sweeping presuppositions of this statement uncritically, the very rationale for this article would be invalidated. We don't fail to see in what sense the claims of Salwi could be justified. However, on the other hand, there is a hidden conceptual submission here to the Western understanding of science, the exclusivist self-vision of which does not let any regional concern in science. While such negations may be justified within the strict contours of the definition of science, a courageous openness to challenge and revision the fundamentals of that which constitutes the scientific enterprise would necessarily invite the rich elusiveness and uniqueness of the regional sciences to the mainstream science. My initiation to the Indian scientific tradition compels me to adjudge the above-mentioned claims as untenable for there are several elements that render the Indian scientific legacy to be specifically Indian. And this unique legacy has something in it to revamp the global momentum of the science-spirituality dialogue.

In the first part of this article, we will take a panoramic view of the Indian scientific tradition particularly from the perspective of astronomy, mathematics and medicine. Then we discuss some of the central epistemological tenets of the Indian scientific tradition, which is accountable for its ontological proximity with philosophy and religion culminating in a scientifically warranted spiritual holism. We conclude with some observations on what the global science-religion momentum can benefit from the science-religion equilibrium of India.

1. Indian Scientific Legacy

Contrary to the popular belief that Indian civilization has been largely "other-worldly," a critical historical scrutiny suggests that some of the greatest Indian minds were much more concerned with developing philosophical paradigms that were grounded in the reality of the secular world. Indian thinking is often criticized for its transcendental dimension. Indian philosophy is more practical than theoretical in the sense that it is concerned with the problems of practical existence. The different schools of Indian philosophy present themselves as the way (*marga*) through correct knowledge (*jnana*) to salvation (*moksa*). To a certain extent, for the Western tradition, the union between body and soul seem to be

confined only to philosophical books. In India, the four *Purusharthas*, viz., *artha*, *kama*, *dharma*, and *moksa* indicate a profoundly integral understanding of the biological, psychological and religious dimensions of human life. There are several prayers in Vedas for material welfare. *Atharvaveda* states that one who worships world alone is in darkness and one who worships God alone is blind.

The scientific temper in India can be easily identified over the past centuries. The solely mystical and intuitive representation of Indian philosophy is, to some extent, a colonial product which obfuscates a rich tradition of scientific thought and analysis in India.

But even amongst those Indian philosophers who accepted the separation of mind and body and argued for the existence of the soul, there was considerable dedication to the scientific method and to developing the principles of deductive and inductive logic. From 1000 B.C to the 4th C A.D (also described as India's rationalistic period) treatises in astronomy, mathematics, logic, medicine and linguistics were produced. The philosophers of the Sankhya school, the Nyaya-Vaisesika schools and early Jain and Buddhist scholars made substantial contributions to the growth of science and learning. . . . In particular, the rational period produced some of the most fascinating series of debates on what constitutes the 'scientific method': How does one separate our sensory perceptions from dreams and hallucinations? When does an observation of reality become accepted as fact, and as scientific truth? How should the principles of inductive and deductive logic be developed and applied? How does one evaluate a hypothesis for its scientific merit? What is a valid inference? What constitutes a scientific proof? These and other questions were attacked with an unexpected intellectual vigour.³

Indians have been the pioneers in the field of astronomy and medicine and several other physical sciences. The study of *Ganit* i.e., mathematics was given considerable importance in the Vedic period. The *Vedang Jyotish* (1000 BC) includes the statement: "Just as the feathers of a peacock and the jewel-stone of a snake are placed at the highest point of the body (at the forehead), similarly, the position of *Ganit* is the highest amongst all branches of the *Vedas* and the *Sastras*." The same emphasis could be found in the statement of Jain mathematician from Mysore, Mahaviracharya, who further emphasized the importance

of mathematics: "Whatever object exists in this moving and non-moving world, cannot be understood without the base of *Ganit*."

Arithmetic operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, fractions, squares, cubes and roots are enumerated in the *Narad Vishnu Purana* attributed to Ved Vyas (pre-1000 BC). Examples of geometric knowledge (*rekha-ganit*) are to be found in the *Sulva-Sutras* of Baudhayana (800 BC). The description of the techniques for the construction of the ritual altars in *Apasthamba* (600 BC) is suggestive as to how scientific knowledge is tapped for religious purposes. Baudhayana's *Sutra* displays an understanding of basic geometric shapes and techniques of converting one geometric shape (such as a rectangle) to another of equivalent (or multiple, or fractional) area (such as a square). Most of these formulations are found to be accurate barring some approximations, revealing a certain degree of practical ingenuity as well as some theoretical understanding of basic geometric principles. Modern methods of multiplication and addition probably emerged from the techniques described in the *Sulva-Sutras*.⁴

There are also studies suggesting that the great Greek mathematician and philosopher, Pythagoras, was influenced by the Upanishads and developed his geometry from the *Sulva-Sutra*. *Apasthamba's sutra*, which is an expansion of Baudhayana's works, provides a value for the square root of 2 that is accurate to the fifth decimal place. *Apasthamba* also looked at the problems of squaring a circle, dividing a segment into seven equal parts, and a solution to the general linear equation. These examples show how vigorous was the mathematical awareness of ancient India.

A significant observation which is relevant for our contention of the interaction between science and religion is the impact of the philosophical traditions upon the development of the mathematical formulations. Jainism and Buddhism have exerted large philosophical influence on the mathematical assumptions of the ancient period. Jainism along with the Upanishads believed in limitless space and time. This led to a deep interest in very large numbers and definitions of infinite numbers. Permutations and combinations are listed in the *Bhagvati Sutras* (3rd C BC) and *Sathananga Sutra* (2nd C BC).

Jain set theory probably arose in parallel with the *Syadvada* system of Jain epistemology in which reality was described in terms of pairs of truth conditions and state changes. The *Anuyoga Dwara Sutra* demonstrates an understanding of the law of indices and uses it to develop the notion of logarithms. Terms like *ardh aached*, *trik aached* and *chatur aached* are used to denote log base 2, log base 3 and log base 4 respectively. In *Satkhandagama* various sets are operated upon by logarithmic functions to base two, by squaring and extracting square roots, and by raising to finite or infinite powers. The operations are repeated to produce new sets. In other works the relation of the number of combinations to the coefficients occurring in the binomial expansion is noted. Since Jain epistemology allowed for a degree of indeterminacy in describing reality, it probably helped in grappling with indeterminate equations⁵ and finding numerical approximations to irrational numbers.

The Buddhist philosophical literature also was instrumental in the formulations concerning *Sunya*. “Philosophical formulations concerning *Sunya* - i.e. emptiness or the void may have facilitated in the introduction of the concept of zero. While the zero (*bindu*) as an empty place holder in the place-value numeral system appears much earlier, algebraic definitions of the zero and its relationship to mathematical functions appear in the mathematical treatises of Brahmagupta in the 7th CAD. Although scholars are divided about how early the symbol for zero came to be used in numeric notation in India, tangible evidence for the use of the zero begins to proliferate towards the end of the Gupta period.”⁶ Buddhist mathematics was classified either as *Garna* (Simple Mathematics) or *Sankhyan* (Higher Mathematics). Numbers were deemed to be of three types: *Sankheya* (countable), *Asankheya* (uncountable) and *Anant* (infinite).

Inidans had remarkable achievements in the field of astronomy and cosmology. Aryabhatta, Varahamihira, Bhaskara, etc. are the leading astronomers in the Indian history. Aryabhatta made pioneering discoveries in the realm of planetary motion. This led to advances in the definition of space and time measuring units and better comprehension of concepts such as gravitation, motion and velocity.⁷ The study of astronomy also led to a great interest in quantifying very large and very small units of time and space. Aryabhatta provided a systematic treatment of the position

of the planets in space. Aryabhatta had a profound influence on the astronomers and mathematicians who followed him. He had a remarkably close approximations on pi and the circumference of the earth. Bhaskara I continued where Aryabhatta left off, and discussed in further detail topics such as the longitudes of the planets, conjunctions of the planets with each other and with bright stars, risings and settings of the planets, and the lunar crescent.⁸ Another important astronomer was Varahamira (6th C, Ujjain) who made important additions to Aryabhatta’s trigonometric formulas. His works on permutations and combinations complemented what had been previously achieved by Jain mathematicians. In the 7th century, Brahmagupta did important works in enumerating the basic principles of algebra.

The geographical factors like the need to have accurate calendars and a better understanding of climate and rainfall patterns for timely sowing and choice of crops also necessitated the development of astronomy. Meanwhile, it is also observed that religion and astrology also played a role in creating an interest in astronomy.

One of the most scientific of the scientific achievements of India is in the field of Medicine. Ayurveda is India’s ancient holistic healing science. Considered to be the “Mother of all healing,” it is claimed by some to be more than 6,000 years old. This system is neatly and intimately intertwined with the religious, philosophical and cultural traditions of India. According to this system, the source of disease is in a complex interconnected web of factors in the body, mind and spirit. Hence treatment aims fundamentally at bringing about a harmony between the physical, emotional, mental and spiritual dimensions and functions of humans. Hence Charaka says, “The whole of suffering which cleaves mind and body has ignorance for its basis, and conversely, all happiness is found in clear scientific knowledge.” “That is named Ayurveda (the science of life) wherein is laid down the principles of the good and bad life.”⁹ Ayurveda is a practical science of life rooted in the harmonious relationship between humans and nature. Ultimate liberation of the Individual is the ultimate concern of Ayurveda.

For Ayurveda, the body-mind dichotomy is artificial. Body is the synchronized conglomeration of the Five Great Elements (*pancha mahabhutas*), viz., earth, water, fire, air, space or *akasa*. When the

variations and combinations of *pancha mahabhutas* are well balanced, the body is intact.¹⁰ Exponents of Ayurveda explained all body functions in relation to the happenings of the universe. All the activities in the human body are grouped into three basic functions of creation, preservation and destruction. The universe is the macrocosm while man is the microcosm. All things in life are interconnected from the essential elemental level.¹¹

Ayurvedic treatment is based upon the ascertainment of the individual constitution. Ayurveda regards disease as a complication of constitutional imbalance. According to Ayurveda there are three bodies attached with our soul – our essential nature, and pure nature, and our Consciousness. (The same applies to Universe). The first one is physical component of the body, the anatomy, the physiology, the biochemistry, the pathology of our body. Second one is Subtle and *Pranic* body – the field of vital energy that is subtler than the electron, proton and neutron of atomic realm. Third is Causal body – the body that is the root of the physical and *Pranic* body. Beyond the three bodies is our essence, our pure consciousness, our soul. Our health depends upon equilibrium of these body parts and their functioning.¹²

2. The Epistemology of the Indian Sciences

Our general historical glance at the development of the various branches of science also suggests how rich they are with philosophical underpinnings and religious overtones, especially, a spiritual holism. This holistic nature of the Indian sciences is owing to the unique epistemological structures of the Indian thinking. Here we attempt to show how a unified approach towards the pursuit after truth has been fragmented by the Western rationalistic determinism which in turn has caused the unwarranted split between science and religion and how the Indian epistemological approach, especially the advaitic (monistic) approach of Hinduism serves as a new hermeneutical tool for a substantive intersection of science and religion. It is our contention that, on the one hand, the logic of integration dominant in the Hindu approach towards reality necessarily entails an ontologically complimentary vision of science and religion, and on the other hand, the emerging epistemological context generated by the compelling scientific knowledge and its methodic and

linguistic commonalities with the religious epistemological structures render their intersection indispensable. The rethinking on revealed knowledge and the recent awareness of the hermeneutical nature of scientific knowledge further corroborate this.

That there is an opaque depth to every ordinary phenomenon has been a predominant insight in several religious and philosophical traditions. While the poetic perception of this depth may lead to the romanticisation of nature, the mystical experience of it may result in the divinization of the world. The awareness of the mysterious depths of the physical reality has been pushed forward to its speculative conclusion in the discovery of an ultimate reality, often termed as God. The mind-set which penetrates into the unseen behind the seen has articulated its experience in divergent theosophies which are cosmocentric in nature. The parallel approach guided by the metaphysical principle, “as the operation is, so the agent,” has also generated its own divine categories with its methodically characteristic preference for analysis over synthesis. While monism and pantheism have been the fate of the former, dualism and transcendentalism were the inevitable corollary of the latter. The absolutist claims of these doctrines not only render these theories often rivals for supremacy, but betray the very content of them to be parochial. The uncritical ontologisation of the experience of the depth in the form of pantheism and monism paves the way to the anarchic identification of God and world, and the naive dualism and transcendentalism may be causative of fragmentation and alienation between God and world.

Notwithstanding the substantial speculative achievements of this cosmocentric or at least cosmically conditioned theosophies, the conceptual limitations exhibited by them pause before us serious questions concerning their developmental strategy and speculative methodology. Despite the mystical perception of a depth in each physical reality, the subsequent process of ontologisation has been marked by a considerable amount of ignorance of the very content of the physical reality. A basic presupposition that can be traced back to the very beginning of speculative philosophy and predominantly explicated by the Platonists is that matter is passive, dead, inert, void and formless. The concepts of space, time, etc. were considered insignificant in the scholastic thought as they were only the accidental properties of a being. An inadequate understanding

of the structure and constitution of the physical reality and an underestimation of its implications in the speculative process have produced a lot of conceptual loopholes and imaginative jumps in several metaphysical doctrines. This basic epistemological vagueness at the starting point of our pursuit after truth has in a way resulted in a conceptual crisis as regards the ultimate questions, and brought us to the verge of the present cultural inferno.

The science-religion tension, too, is a conceptual outcome of this ontologically alienated and epistemologically misinformed evolutionary development of the human knowledge-enterprise. The European romanticisation of science as the only or the most supreme form of knowledge was basically the outcome of an ontologically and epistemically deviated state of affairs. The ontological dualism in the form of an anthropocentric worldview was corroborated by an epistemological dualism as found in the logical system of Aristotelian logic of identity with its anthropocentric bifurcation and the resulting binaries. The anthropocentric epistemology envisaged a hierarchy of knowledge having graded inequality. The inductive method of science is in a way a consort to this Aristotelian logic of identity in difference. This logic of difference can promote only a compartmentalized view of reality with its divergent disciplines often in rivalry with each other. Physicist Bernard D'espagnat, is quite right in his observation: "Systematic thought is gravely hampered by an ideal of purity that obliges every specialist, be he a mathematician, a physicist, a biologist, or a philosopher, to contemplate reality solely through the spectacles of his own specialism. Human knowledge is now so extensive that to reflect on the 'great questions' in this restrictive way is to deny ourselves the possibility of a balanced view."¹³¹³ Bernard Despagnat,

Reality and the Physicist - Knowledge, Duration and the Quantum World, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1989, p. 119.

According to Wesley J. Wildman, the root cause of the problematic character of modern Western Culture is a profound confusion, a schizophrenic uncertainty, about how to be in the world, about how to think ethically and scientifically, technologically and worshipfully, critically and religiously.¹⁴

The scientific methodic monism was again perpetuated by the positivist thinking on language and mathematics in modern times. Wittgenstein said there is no linguistically identifiable experience which was exclusively private. Language does very little with the real existent, it is concerned with the universal abstract. Language reduces an existent into an illustrative example of category. My proper name is an acknowledgement of the truth that linguistic concepts are unable to encompass me. Such a way in modern philosophical thinking language and meaning are looked upon more from a social and cultural point of view with very little attention to the metaphysical underpinnings. Such positivist thinking on language also is in a way in the clutches of the Aristotelian logic of identity in difference.¹⁵ The social and cultural platforms of interpretations alone are no adequate grounds for a substantive interface of science and religion.

Barring these philosophical appropriations of truth, does the religious knowledge, with its supernatural foundations on revelation, offer us a complete and integral account of truth? In fact, a glimpse into the very landscape where revelation and revealed knowledge find its shape and expression compel us to answer in the negative. Often, the conceptual panorama of the speculative knowledge serves as the epistemological background in which the hermeneutic of religious knowledge takes place. Hence the concept-laden categories of revelation cannot be expected to offer us an easy outlet from this epistemological imbroglio.

What we need is an epistemology that is capable of dealing with human and his context with all its expressions in life, action, language, art and culture as an integral unit. Despite the absolutist or sometimes the contrary reductionist strategy of speculative knowledge and the supernatural nature of the revelation, a basic methodological presupposition in both of these approaches has been the dialectical relationship between God and the world in unraveling the mystery of each other. The mystery of the 'invisible' God can be explained by unfolding the physical mystery of the visible universe and vice versa. Avoiding the pitfalls of the above-mentioned uncritical ontologisations, building upon this fundamental presupposition by discovering a new integral epistemology may throw us into many so far undreamt wonderlands of knowledge.

This ontological proximity between God and world does not seem to have obtained due hermeneutical attention in the interpretative circles of science and religion in the Western tradition. It is in this background of the need for an epistemological development from a methodological monism to a methodological pluralism that the advaitic epistemology of the Indian tradition is to be evaluated as a viable alternative hermeneutical tool.

The experiential basis of knowledge is the key factor here. The advaitic epistemology begins with experience and ends in experience and knowledge is experience itself. This position is different from the rationalistic and empiricist tradition of Western epistemology. The Western Epistemology distinguishes between subject, object and knowledge. Hence each form of knowledge is different from the other. This method tends to present the claims of Art, Literature, Science and Religion, etc. as mutually exclusive disciplines. While the dualistic categories of the West tends to be mutually exclusive, the unified and synthetic vision of the East tends to be mutually completing. For the Hindu epistemology, even the compartmentalized treatment of science and religion is the outcome of *avidya* or ignorance, let alone the conflict between science and religion. The Hindu intelligence is always one-pointed. This is often termed as one-centredness or *ekanishtata*. According to Brahmabandhab Upadhyay, *ekanishtata* (One-centredness) is the essence of the Hindu's Hinduness.

The relation of non-difference between Agent and effect, the appearance in reflecting creation of a reflective Creator, the deceptive manifoldness of the (One) without a second, have (all) nourished the one-pointed intuitive vision of the seers. . . . The tendency to one-centred thinking, the seeing into the thinghood of a thing (*bastur bastutvadarsan*), the experience of ultimate non-difference between Agent and effect, the knowledge of the deceptiveness (*mayikata*) of multiplicity, comprise the Hindu's Hinduness.¹⁶

K. S. Radhakrishnan finds the Upanishadic Mahavakya (Great Saying) *Ayam Athmam Brahmam* as clearly bearing the hallmark of an integral epistemology.¹⁷ In it, the term *ayam* literally means that which moves. Anything that moves is spatio-temporal and anything spatio-temporal can be known by the operation of the sensory and motor organs. Hence *ayam* means anything that can be known by sensory and motor organs. The same experience can be

experienced from the standpoint of the subject who experiences and from the perspective of the object that is being experienced. The *ayam* when it is experienced from the perspective of the subject is known as *atman* (*self*) and when it is experienced and expressed from the perspective of the object is known as Brahman (the Absolute). It is not possible to conceive either subject or object that is different from experiences. The subject, object, process and the product are fused with experience. Such a non-differentiation of experience in which the subject, the object, the process and the product remain as an integrated whole is technically called *ayam*. The changing aspect of *ayam* is termed as *agama* and the non-changing aspect is known as *nigama*. Thus *ayam* is the experience of the *agama* which is based on *nigama*.

Space-time manifestations are the means to experience and express something that is not limited by space and time. This is the hallmark of Indian tradition in general. Words in poetry, sounds in music and colors in painting and body movements in dance are only the various forms of spatio-temporal means to experience and express something that can never be touched by these spatio-temporal limitations. Hence it is said that words are not poetry though poetry is filled with words. Silence is music though an accord of sounds is essential to create music.¹⁸

Given such an ontologically overarching nature of the logic of integration, the Hindu vision postulates no difference between the methodologies of *darsana* (philosophy) and *sastra* (philosophy and science). Every branch of knowledge has the same goal and same methodology. What varies according to disciplines is only the various modes of operation of the same methodology. Hence religion is in a way science and science is in a way religion. Hence in India, philosophy and science have the same goal, i.e. *Ananda*, bliss.¹⁹

The role of science in India is to be assessed from this point of view. Science is termed as *sastra* in India. *Sastra* is different from science in various respects. *Sastra* deals with the foundational, methodological and axiological issues as the indivisible part of its subject matter and course of study. Like science *sastra* relies on experience. But unlike science *sastra* penetrates deep down into the more and more subtle levels by developing the inbuilt natural capacity of the sense organs. The experience of *agama* and *nigama* can be expressed in many forms and *sastra* is only one among them and hence *sastra* is not the only form of experience. The whole of reality that is experienced in our

divergent experiences is the *ayam* alone and since there is nothing other than *ayam* that is to be known, every claim to know is only one of the ways of experience and expression of the *ayam* and as such art, literature, religion, science, philosophy, etc. are the different forms of expression of one and the same mode of experience. It is to be noted that Indian *sastra* never makes a distinction between science and technology.

The praxis point of this unified epistemology is the peaceful co-existence of pluralistic perspectives and divergent disciplines and multiple ideologies. Issues like science and religion, fiends or foes or conflict or complementarity are totally alien to the Indian mind-set.

3. Crossing Borders –The Indian Paradigm alongside the Global Momentum

In the light of the historical and epistemological analysis made above, we shall try to highlight the implications of the Indian scientific legacy for the Global momentum of the science-religion dialogue. In India, as we have seen, the origin of science is very much associated with religion. Science initially was an aid to religion. Sacrifice was the prime religious avocation of the Vedic Hindus. Sacrifice was to be performed on an altar of prescribed size and shape. Even the slightest discrepancy in the prescriptions would adversely affect the efficacy of the sacrifices. This in turn was influential in the birth of geometry and mathematics. The birth of geometry was necessitated by finding the proper time and space for the performance of the sacrifice. However, in the course of time, these sciences outgrew their original purpose and came out to be cultivated for their own sake.²⁰²⁰ See Aruna Goel, *Ancient Sankrit Wisdom – Modern Science and Beyond* (New Delhi: Deep and Deep Publications, 2005), p. 19.

As we have seen, the progress of science has also been impacted by religious ideas. Philosophical doctrines also had a profound influence on the development of mathematical concepts and formulations.

When we look at the history of interaction between science and religion in India, it could be observed that it had a liberative potential at the social milieu owing to its challenges to the religious taboos and irrational indoctrination of mystical or magical phenomenon, as is universally

characteristic of science. In the Greek science, we find the then cosmologists shifting the focus from a god-governed universe to a law-governed universe through their scientific activities. Greek astronomers believed in the rationality of nature transcending the limited horizons of mythological doctrines and paving the way to a more objective and rational appropriation of the cosmic phenomenon. Adherence to false superstitions can often pose serious impediments to the advance of science.

Societies that believed that only the ‘gods’ knew the secrets of nature and that it was futile for humans to attempt to unravel the mysteries of the universe were naturally incapable of making any substantial progress in the realm of the sciences. Even in societies where there were no formal religious taboos in understanding real-world phenomenon in a scientific way, the power and the influence of the priests could serve as an obstacle to scientific progress. For instance, in a society where ritual practices alone were considered sufficient in achieving desired goals, there would naturally be little scope for serious investigation into the properties and laws of nature. While ancient India did not generally suffer from the first affliction (of religious opposition to science), it did suffer from the second (the proliferation of rituals and superstitions). The progress of science in India was thus inextricably linked to challenges to the domination of the priests, and resistance to the proliferation of rituals and sacrifices.²¹

Scientific thinking in India has forced at least a sect of the society to think that rituals alone were insufficient in producing desired results, and that some measure of rational observation of the world was necessary in shaping human destiny. “It is therefore no accident that, by and large, developments in science and technology came in parallel with the advance of rational philosophy in India.”²² That is why Indian scientists in the past have recorded useful scientific observations without serious attempts at quantification, or deeper investigation into the physical and chemical causes of what they observed. While the ancient Indian astronomy was based on proper scientific methods, in other fields of scientific investigation, Indian scientists seemed to remain content with intuitive and general observations, tolerating a far greater degree of vagueness and imprecision. This was because astronomy was triggered partly by practical considerations such as the need for accurate monsoon prediction and rainfall mapping, but perhaps even more so, by the growing demand for

“good” astrologers. The obsession with astrological charts - both amongst the royalty and mercantile classes led to considerable state patronage of intellectuals who wished to pursue the study of astronomy.²³

As a remnant of the religious obsessions, even today in India, there is a very negative trend towards the romanticisation of the ancient Indian scientific tradition often rating its chronological precedence as a quantitative and qualitative superiority over the Western tradition. “Everything was stated long ago in the Vedas” is the clichéd jargon. Indian Science-religion dialogue has a tendency to go by an uncritical juxtaposing of the two rather than a more ontological and hermeneutical interface of science and religion. A deeper religious hermeneutic of the Indian tradition of science may alleviate the superficial treatment of the same and place the present-day science-religion dialogue in India on its proper and authentic platform.

A religious appropriation of the specific characteristics of the Indian sciences can make the science-religion momentum to be truly global. While the science-religion enterprise in the West is very much dominated by the inter-placement of the natural sciences and the Christian theology, the Eastern scientific and religious traditions are yet to establish themselves in this emerging interdisciplinary field.

A dialogue between the Indian sciences and the Western sciences can restore to science its lost aesthetic elegance and moral charm which could conversely promote the proximity between science and religion on methodological and axiological grounds. In terms of pedagogy, it is said that there is an excessive abstraction in most text books, and undue theoretical complexity is thrust upon students. In contrast, the Indian approach with its stress on observation of natural phenomenon, and epistemological approach to understanding each field with a good intuitive way of perceiving scientific phenomenon can be more appealing.²⁴ In the contemporary natural sciences, we witness an emerging mystification of the sciences at the top of the ascending scientific inquiry. Meanwhile the Indian tradition testifies to a descending mystery from the cosmic level to the phenomenal level of the sciences. This dialogue can analogically boost the scientific re-mystification of nature and cosmos.

The societal and ethical commitments of the natural sciences can be reinforced and redefined quite radically by the existential and religious *sitz im leben* of the Indian scientific tradition. The polarity between the scientific discovery and the ethical questions discovered today will be almost unwarranted provided we develop adequate methodological tools and set humanistically and cosmically sound goals and objectives for the scientific enterprise after the model of the Indian tradition. For instance, the Ayurvedic ethics is summed up in Susruta’s dictum: “He who regards kindness to himself and to humanity as his supreme dharma and treats his patients accordingly, succeeds best in achieving the aims of life and obtains the greatest happiness.” The following statements from the ancient texts give a glimpse into the cosmic ethical sensitivity in the ancient medical tradition of India. “The physician should regard all his patients as if they were his own children and vigilantly guard them from all harm, considering this to be his highest *dharma* (duty)”; “Those whose compassion for all creatures is great and who are devoted to truth are ever zealous in putting down false doctrines”; “The patient who may distrust his own parents, sons and relations should repose an imperfect faith in his own physician and put his own life in his hands without apprehension of danger.

Hence a physician should protect his patient as his own begotten child.” Epistemological enhancement is another area where the global science-religion momentum can profit from the Indian tradition. While in the West our picture of reality is partly constructed by our epistemological and methodological tools, in the East the Experience of Reality dictates our methodological and epistemological structures. In India, the divergent experiences of reality at their core have a unifying experience which accommodates even the diametrically opposite representations without conflict, rather as complementary. Hence we need to think whether a case to case dialogue between science and religion would suffice, or do we need to begin with a metaphysical bedrock anchoring upon which we address the oscillating challenges from science, which would make religion more confident and not

to tremble at any new scientific discovery. It is to be noted in this context that in sharp contrast to the Western logic which inquires whether the form of a proposition and argument is true, the Indian logic is based on the conviction that logic is an instrument for the discovery and understanding of reality, and not a mere formal discipline wholly unrelated to the world. Indian logicians reject the verbalist view that logic is only concerned with thought-forms and symbols and not with content and referents. Such radical rethinking on our epistemological tools is essential for developing some perennial conceptual structures for the dialogue between science and religion.

The hermeneutical appropriation of the spiritual vision behind the Indian sciences can very well add an affective and emotive dimension to the Western interdisciplinary attempts dominated by the cognitive and rationalistic approaches. There is more to the science-religion dialogue than mere conceptual clarifications or theoretical rapprochement, which is the dominating trend in this field as of now. In bridging the gap between the brain and the heart in this field, the Indian science-religion paradigm is of vital significance. The activity of knowledge in India remains incomplete without embracing the praxis level. The penetrating question of the *guru* (teacher) to the *sisya* (disciple) was whether he possessed that, by possessing which he possessed everything else or whether he knew that by knowing which he knew everything else. That is why in India, there is a difference between knowledge and wisdom. Knowledge is something that is absorbing one's total person. In translating the plethora of activities in the interdisciplinary field of science and religion to such an absorbing, scintillating and enchanting experience of learning and living, the substantively holistic nuances of the science-religion unity of India may be availed of.

Conclusion

I have a feeling that there is too much of science-religion dialogue in the Western academic circles without clarifying the proper foundations and methodologies, without articulating the real goals and objectives, drawing too many parallels often bit superficial. This emerging interdisciplinary attempt needs to be enhanced by transferring its scope

and spheres to more substantial and metaphysical domains of truth. The Indian paradigm where the science-religion dialogue itself is part of a wider spectrum of the manifestation of truth could be helpful in this regard.

Notes

1. Recipient of numerous scientific fellowships and awards, Dr. Augustine Pamplany has published a volley of articles and books in the area of science-religion dialogues. He is also the director of Institute of Science and Religion, Aluva which acts as a catalyst for science-religion dialogues in many parts of India.
2. Dilip M. Salwi, *Nonsense in Indian Science* (Delhi: Konark Publishers Pvt. Ltd., 1998).
3. http://india_resource.tripod.com/scienceh.htm. Pages from the history of the Indian sub-continent: Realism, Skepticism, Rational Thinking, Scientific Progress and Social Ethics.
4. *Ibid.*
5. *Ibid.*
6. *Ibid.*
7. http://india_resource.tripod.com/physics.htm. Pages from the history of the Indian sub-continent: Science and Technology in India.
8. http://india_resource.tripod.com/mathematics.htm. Pages from the history of the Indian sub-continent: Science and Mathematics in India
9. *Charaka Samhitha – Sutra Sthana*, 1: 41.
10. See K U Chacko, "Ayurveda – A Holistic Treatment Born of a Holistic Vision," in *Omega – Indian Journal of Science and Religion*, (2: 2003), pp. 11-12.
11. See *Ibid.*
12. The Holistic nature of Ayurveda or Holistic Ayurveda: <http://www.ayurvedahc.com/articlelive/articles/112/1/The-Holistic-nature-of-Ayurveda-or-Holistic-Ayurveda> by Dr Vikramaditya Tomar, Published on 04/22/2005.

14. See Wesley J. Wildman, "The Quest for Harmony - An Interpretation of Contemporary Theology and Science," W. Mark Richardson and Wesley J. Wildman (eds.), *Religion and Science - History, Method, Dialogue*, (New York: Routledge, 1996), p. 44.
15. See K. S. Radhakrishnan, Science, Technology and Values – An Indian Perspective, Paper presented in CTNS-SRCP Workshop in Pune, India, December, 2001, pp. 14-16.
16. Brahmabandhab Upadhyay, "The One-Centredness of the Hindu Race," J. J. Lipner, (tr.), *Vidyajyoti Journal of Theological Reflections*, LXI, Oct. 1981, p. 419, 421.
17. See K. S. Radhakrishnan.
18. Ibid., p. 14.
19. Ibid.
21. http://india_resource.tripod.com/physics.htm. Pages from the history of the Indian sub-continent: Science and Technology in India.
22. Ibid.
23. See Ibid.
24. See Ibid.

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The Meaning of Life

- K. Babu Joseph¹

Terry Eagleton. *The Meaning of Life*, Oxford University Press, Indian Edition, 2008, New Delhi.

This compact book, set out in less than 200 pages, by Terry Eagleton, John Edwards Taylor, Professor of English at the University of Manchester, a fellow of the British Academy, and a writer of international repute, poses one of the most difficult questions man has been asking from time immemorial and veers to an answer hatched in the author's thought. Though the last word on the question reflects his own attitudes, a lot of discussion precedes it. One's meaning of life, according to him, is not a solution to a problem but a matter of living in a certain way that is ethical rather than metaphysical. It is society's life which is meaningful and not that of individual. A society bound by the thread of agape or love has discovered the meaning of life.

The book has four chapters. The first chapter carries out a detailed analysis of the philosophical as well as logical nature of questions and answers. Invoking Ludwig Wittgenstein's ideas on linguistic analysis, he critically examines the import of the phrases meaning and life. The statement 'what is the meaning of life' is different from the statement 'what is the capital of Albania,' even though both are of the same grammatical structure. The first structure lacks clarity in the corresponding signifier-signified relationship, while the second one is amply clear. Words have no intrinsic meaning of their own. It is the context which imparts meaning to words. Despite its woolliness, the very fact that we talk about the meaning of life, makes the question non-trivial.

Not being able to understand the mystery of life, man lives under the constant shadow of death. For believers in god, there is a ready-